

INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS AND COMMUNICATION

¹Aripova N.A., ²Nigmatov O. R.

¹Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Associate Professor of the Department of Uzbek Language and Literature

²Student of the Moscow State Technological University named after Stankin

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Abstract. *This article examines the importance of intercultural awareness and communication and its role in ensuring mutual understanding, peace, and stability in a global society. It emphasizes the importance of empathy, compassion, and tolerance in intercultural dialogue, and the need to respect and understand cultural differences. Also, the importance of developing intercultural awareness and effectively organizing communication in social and global cooperation was demonstrated, showing that it can lead to positive changes on a global scale.*

Keywords: *intercultural awareness, intercultural communication, mutual understanding, global cooperation, cultural differences, peace and stability, love and tolerance, respect for cultures and international relations.*

INTRODUCTION In today's era of globalization, communication and dialogue between different cultures are becoming increasingly important. Dialogue between cultures is considered an important tool not only for promoting international cooperation, but also for ensuring peace and stability between societies. This process requires empathy, compassion, and patience, and also helps to understand and respect different cultural differences. Intercultural awareness and communication is the process of establishing effective dialogue and ensuring mutual understanding between people of different cultures. To successfully implement this process, it is necessary to understand, respect, and value cultural differences.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS. Intercultural awareness is the ability of people to understand and respect different cultures, to understand the differences between them, and to build productive relationships by taking these differences into account. Awareness requires, first of all, empathy and compassion, because each culture has its own values, customs, language, and worldview. Intercultural awareness also involves recognizing and respecting the differences between one's own culture and the cultures of others.

Developing intercultural awareness helps people gain a broader worldview. Learning English not only broadens knowledge of different cultures, but also helps people better understand themselves and others. It also helps them to actively participate in intercultural dialogue, develop mutual respect and tolerance, and ensure a high level of cooperation between people of different backgrounds and perspectives. A love of cultural change and a positive attitude towards it are essential in developing intercultural awareness. This plays a vital role in building trust and respect among people and ensuring global stability. Thus, intercultural awareness is a key factor necessary to strengthen not only personal but also societal ties and to appreciate cultural diversity. Intercultural communication is a process of communication between individuals belonging to two or more cultures, the goal of which is to achieve mutual understanding and agreement. Intercultural communication is complicated by language, signs, behavior, and other cultural factors. Communication methods and reception styles may differ between different cultures, so individuals

who practice such communication strive to understand the culture of others using their own cultural codes.

Intercultural communication is a set of various forms of relations and communication between individuals and groups belonging to different cultures [1]. A. R. Sadokhin emphasizes, "Intercultural communication is a set of forms of relations and communication between individuals and groups belonging to different cultures" [2;112]. T. B. Frick calls it "a meeting of representatives of different cultures" [3;100]. I.V. Denisova and A.R. Yeremenko also give a similar classification: "interethnic communication is a meeting between people of different nationalities" [4]. V.S. Bibler [5;417], speaking about intercultural communication, describes free relations in the field of intercultural communication as a special social form, a new vision of culture. The main issue here is the obstacles to communication. T. N. Rersikova defines this concept as a cultural process based on cultural (national) close relations related to the participants in the communication process [6].

In such communication, it is necessary to take into account the specific characteristics of cultures, because in communication between different peoples and ethnic groups, ambiguity, misunderstanding, or even misinterpretation may arise. For example, while some cultures favor direct and affectionate communication, others require softening of language or behavior to convey kindness and gentleness. As a result, for cross-cultural communication to be effective, both parties must respect their own culture and strive to understand the values of others. The success of intercultural communication depends not only on language proficiency, but also on developing intercultural skills, demonstrating empathy, self-understanding, and accepting the culture of others. For this reason, empathy, compassion, and patience are key factors in developing intercultural communication. Such communication serves as an important tool for global cooperation, social stability, and appreciation of cultural diversity.

Language itself is of great importance in every culture. Words and expressions have a certain meaning and understanding in one culture, but their meaning may change in another culture. Therefore, linguistic sensitivity is necessary for learning a language and communicating effectively between people in cross-cultural communication. For example, the English phrase "how are you?" is not used as a formal question, but as a friendly question. In some cultures, such a question can actually be taken as a serious question about the person's condition. Examples like these demonstrate the importance of understanding language and the subtle differences in words in cross-cultural communication.

Gestures, facial expressions, body language, and other nonverbal cues can vary across cultures. For example, in one culture, smiling may convey warmth and friendliness, while in another, it may evoke feelings of weakness or hostility. As another example, in some cultures, nodding is also used to indicate rejection or objection, such as in Middle Eastern cultures. Such differences can lead to misunderstandings in cross-cultural communication, so it is important to take into account the importance of nonverbal signals.

Another difference between cultures is how time is perceived and managed. While some cultures have a strict and well-defined time frame, others may have a more relaxed approach to time. For example, in Western cultures, time is clearly and strictly managed, with everything having to be done at its appointed time. In contrast, Eastern cultures tend to be more conservative and lax in time management, where latecomers are common. It is important to respectfully clarify how time is understood and accepted in intercultural communication. By understanding these

differences, people can develop empathy and tolerance for one another. Respect for religious and ethnic differences is also important in cross-cultural communication. Failure to fully understand or accept the religious beliefs and customs of others can lead to conflict in communication. Therefore, being careful and attentive in intercultural communication, as well as respecting the values of others, helps to ensure successful communication. All of this shows that intercultural communication requires not only language, but also a deep understanding of the common values and characteristics of cultures. Only on the basis of such understanding and respect can real and productive dialogue be established.

To develop intercultural awareness, it is first necessary to understand and respect your own culture. This not only helps you to better understand the values of your own culture, but also plays an important role in establishing productive and respectful relationships with others. It is also important to develop self-awareness to be open-minded and accepting of other cultures. The following tips can help you develop cross-cultural awareness:

Every culture has its own history, values, customs, and traditions. Learning about these can help you understand the workings of cultures and the reasons for their formation. Knowing how different cultures have developed in a historical context can help you better understand their values and customs.

In intercultural communication, it is important to understand the thoughts and feelings of other people and put yourself in their shoes. This makes the communication sincere and respectful. Intercultural communication helps to understand the point of view of others and creates the opportunity to accept them sincerely

Courses and trainings on intercultural communication help young people become knowledgeable in this field. Trainings help individuals understand and respect cultural differences and establish effective communication. Intercultural education is essential for improving global relations and teaching the right approach in a changing world.

It is natural to make mistakes in intercultural communication, but what is important is to learn from these mistakes and learn how to deal with them in the right way. Understanding and learning from mistakes leads to the development of communication and creates the opportunity to be more open and accepting of other cultures.

Developing empathy and analyzing your own culture will help you interact more closely and respectfully with others. Personal experiences and interactions with others are essential for developing cross-cultural awareness.

Developing intercultural awareness is not only an important means of personal growth, but also of establishing peace, stability, and mutual respect in society. The process helps to develop a wide range of dialogues between different cultures, which creates opportunities for acceptance of differences and mutual understanding in a global society. Intercultural awareness creates the basis for honest and sincere dialogue between people, contributing to social stability on a global scale. Of course, this strengthens understanding and cooperation between different peoples and cultures. For example, promoting an intercultural approach in society fosters mutual respect between people of different nationalities, religions, and languages, and reduces stereotypes and discrimination.

Intercultural awareness not only helps to maintain peace, but is also an important step towards achieving social equality and justice. Acceptance and mutual understanding of cultural differences ensure greater cooperation and improved social relations between groups that are isolated in society.

Thus, the development of intercultural awareness leads not only to personal growth, but also to the stable development and peaceful coexistence of the entire society. The formation of intercultural awareness helps people accept and respect the differences between different peoples and cultures. This process is an important element of mutual understanding, strengthening peace in society. Another important aspect is that intercultural awareness strengthens global cooperation and is a catalyst for positive change on an international scale. Conflicts between societies will decrease, and opportunities for jointly solving major international problems will expand.

Improving intercultural communication not only ensures effective communication, but also helps to develop mutual respect and cooperation. As a result, trust and unity between societies are strengthened. The development of intercultural awareness also plays an important role in ensuring social stability and preventing wars and conflicts. The main factor that helps to build a new, stable and safe world is intercultural understanding and solidarity.

Furthermore, the development of intercultural awareness expands opportunities for education and knowledge exchange, which in turn helps to promote innovations and progressive ideas. In this way, intercultural dialogue and the rise of awareness on a global scale contribute significantly to ensuring peaceful coexistence, sustainable development and social equality among the peoples of the world.

Intercultural awareness and communication play an important role in establishing successful relationships on pressing social, economic, and political issues in today's society. The importance of intercultural dialogue in maintaining mutual understanding and peace on a global scale is growing. The interaction between different cultures undoubtedly plays an important role in ensuring stability and social justice in the world. Intercultural dialogue, as well as strengthening economic and political cooperation, greatly contributes to the social and economic development of nations. At the same time, promoting intercultural communication and awareness reduces the difficulties and conflicts that arise in society during the process of globalization, as people learn to respect different cultural values and practices.

CONCLUSION: Developing intercultural awareness and learning to communicate is essential to building more sincere, respectful, and stable relationships around the world. This process helps individuals to deeply understand their own cultures and to see other cultures as equals. Intercultural communication fosters mutual respect and understanding, further strengthening social bonds. Communication based on open-mindedness and acceptance of cultural diversity creates productive interactions between individuals and groups.

The development of intercultural communication leads to positive changes not only at the personal level, but also in global society. This process, of course, helps to strengthen mutual understanding and effective communication between people. The development of intercultural communication and consciousness creates opportunities for the exchange of knowledge and ideas. It also encourages the establishment of effective and stable relations between international organizations and societies, because through mutual understanding and respect, it becomes easier to find solutions to international problems. Such development brings about positive changes in the fields of trade, politics, culture and education.

Intercultural awareness and communication, on the one hand, help to eliminate stereotypes and prejudices between different peoples. On the other hand, this process also plays an important role in maintaining peace in international situations and preventing wars. To reduce cultural conflicts and strengthen peace, people need to understand each other's values and customs. The

development of intercultural awareness fosters mutual respect between individuals and societies, creating the possibility of a more stable and just world in the future.

In this way, intercultural awareness and communication serve as a necessary tool not only to ensure peace and stability in society, but also to achieve better understanding and cooperation between different peoples and cultures. This helps to ensure peace, stability, and social development not only internationally, but also at every level, from individuals to social groups. Intercultural communication not only strengthens global ties around the world, but also creates the opportunity to implement positive changes within societies.

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